

Original Research

Floristic Diversity and Halophytic Plant Communities of Lake Sif Lemnadi, Northern Sahara (Algeria)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyse the ecological and chorological characteristics of the flora of Lake Sif Lemnadi, located in the southeastern Saharan region of Algeria, to better understand this arid ecosystem's composition and floristic diversity. A biocoenotic analysis was carried out on four plots distributed according to the cardinal points of the site. In total, 14 species belonging to 9 families and 14 genera were recorded. Chamaephytes (50%) represented the dominant biological type, followed by hemicryptophytes (21.4%). For the frequency classes, the most represented categories were the very accidental and common species, each accounting for 42.9%. Perennial herbaceous plants dominated the morphological spectrum (50%). From a chorological perspective, species classified as Saharan elements were the best represented (35.7%). The vegetation cover ranged from 11.2% to 24.4%. The vegetation cover rate varied between 11.2% and 24.4%. The lakeshore vegetation was primarily dominated by halophytic species, mainly from the Amaranthaceae family. The variation in the total halophyte cover among plots was not influenced by their geographical orientation. These results highlight the ecological importance of Lake Sif Lemnadi as a refuge for Saharan halophytic communities and provide a baseline reference for the monitoring and conserving saline wetlands in Saharan contexts.

Keywords

Lake Sif Lemnadi, Sahara, Algeria, floristic diversity, biological types, halophytes.

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Floristična raznovrstnost in halofitske rastlinske skupnosti jezera Sif Lemnadi, severna Sahara (Alžirija)

Izvleček

Namen te študije je analizirati ekološke in korološke značilnosti flore jezera Sif Lemnadi, ki se nahaja v jugovzhodnem saharskem območju Alžirije, da bi bolje razumeli sestavo in floristično raznolikost tega sušnega ekosistema. Biocenotska analiza je bila izvedena na štirih parcelah, razporejenih glede na svetovne strani lokacije. Skupaj je bilo zabeleženih 14 vrst, ki pripadajo 9 družinam in 14 rodovom. Chamaefiti (50 %) so predstavljali prevladujoč biološki tip, sledili pa so jim hemikriptofiti (21,4 %). Glede na pogostost so bile najbolj zastopane kategorije zelo naključne in pogoste vrste, ki so predstavljale 42,9 %. Morfološko so prevladovala trajna zeliščna (50 %). S horološkega vidika so bile najbolj zastopane vrste, uvrščene med saharske elemente (35,7 %). Rastlinska pokrovnost je znašala od 11,2 % do 24,4 %. Stopnja rastlinske pokrovnosti je nihala med 11,2 % in 24,4 %. Ob jezeru je prevladovala predvsem halofitska flora, predvsem iz družine Amaranthaceae. Na razliko v skupni pokritosti s halofiti med parcelami ni vplivala njihova geografska usmerjenost. Ti rezultati poudarjajo ekološki pomen jezera Sif Lemnadi kot zatočišča za saharske halofitske skupnosti in zagotavljajo osnovno referenco za spremljanje in ohranjanje slanih mokrišč v saharskih kontekstih.

Ključne besede

Jezero Sif Lemnadi, Sahara, Alžirija, rastlinska raznovrstnost, biološki tipi, halofiti.

Introduction

Wetlands, long regarded as secondary habitats, play a fundamental role in maintaining biodiversity and regulating essential ecological cycles (Requier-Desjardins et al., 2021). In the Mediterranean region, they represent true hotspots of biological diversity, hosting plant and animal communities adapted to contrasting environmental conditions (Quézel & Santa, 1962).

Chotts and sebkhas are endorheic saline depressions typical of arid North Africa. Chotts are shallow basins that flood temporarily before drying into salt flats, while sebkhas are more permanently saline areas where groundwater and evaporation maintain moist, salty soils. Both host halophytic vegetation adapted to high salinity and water stress (Khaznadar et al., 2009).

In arid and semi-arid zones, such as the Algerian Sahara, chotts and sebkhas are of particular ecological importance as refuges for specialised flora. Chotts and sebkhas are endorheic (closed) saline depressions typical of arid North Africa. Chotts are shallow basins that can temporarily flood during rare rainfall events, forming ephemeral lakes that later dry out into salt flats. Sebkhas, in contrast, are more permanently saline areas where high groundwater tables

and intense evaporation maintain moist, salty soils throughout much of the year. These hydrosaline environments create harsh conditions with high salinity and water stress, yet they support the persistence of halophytic and succulent species highly adapted to such edaphic constraints (Khaznadar et al., 2009; Kaabeche et al., 1993; Pearce & Crivelli, 1994; Khan et al., 2006; Öztürk et al., 2011). Among the most representative plant families are the Amaranthaceae, particularly the genera *Atriplex*, *Suaeda*, *Salsola*, and *Salicornia* (Brown, 2006; Koull, 2023). These ecosystems contribute to biodiversity conservation and ecosystem resilience under both climatic variability and anthropogenic pressures (Benabadji et al., 2010; Chafic et al., 2013).

Algeria hosts more than 2,000 wetlands, of which 50 are listed under the Ramsar Convention, covering an area of nearly 3 million hectares (Balla, 2012). Most of these sites are concentrated in the eastern High Plateaus, where endorheic wetlands of high ecological value dominate. The Sahara, which covers more than 85% of the national territory, also harbours unique ecosystems such as sebkhas, chotts, and oases, where water availability strongly shapes the composition and distribution of plant communities (Marc et al., 2012; Chafic et al., 2013). Although locally rich in species, these habitats remain restricted to specific eco-

logical niches. Taxa such as *Salicornia fruticosa* and *Tamarix gallica* illustrate remarkable adaptive strategies to salinity and nutrient-poor soils (Holm et al., 1977; Marc et al., 2012).

Despite the richness and diversity of Algerian wetlands, floristic knowledge of these ecosystems remains highly uneven across regions. Most studies conducted to date have primarily focused on the ecology and vegetation of chotts and sebkhas in northern Algeria (Benabadji et al., 2010; Chenchouni, 2017; Bezzalla et al., 2018). In contrast, Saharan wetlands, although characterised by high floristic heterogeneity driven by hydrological fluctuations and saline constraints, remain largely under-documented (Chenchouni, 2012; Koull & Chehma, 2015, 2016; Khechekhouche et al., 2020). This lack of information is particularly pronounced in the endorheic depressions of the eastern Sahara, where variations in salinity and moisture directly influence the distribution, composition, and structure of plant communities (Marco et al., 2010; Štefanić et al., 2019).

Within this context, the floristic study of Lake Sif Lemnadi is of particular scientific interest. Located in the Souf region, this Saharan site remains poorly explored, despite its potential to harbour original plant assemblages shaped by distinctive edaphic constraints. The objective of the present study is therefore to characterise the floristic diversity and ecological traits of the plant communities of this lake, with the aim of filling a significant gap in knowledge of Saharan wetlands and providing essential baseline data for their monitoring and conservation.

Materials and Methods

Study area

Lake Sif Lemnadi (33°57'54" N; 6°22'3.92" E) is a saline wetland typical of Saharan regions (Figure 1). Its high salinity results primarily from soil salt leaching rather than from the composition of groundwater, a phenomenon frequently observed in Saharan wetlands (Koull, 2023).

The lake covers an area of approximately 60.45 hectares (Google Earth, 2019) and is situated at an average altitude of –23 m relative to sea level. Administratively, it is located about 100 km northwest of the capital of El Oued Province, in a region dominated by agricultural activities, particularly date palm cultivation (Voisin, 2004; Halis, 2024).

Climatically, the region is subject to a typical desert climate (BWh according to Köppen), characterised by per-

manent aridity (Côte, 2005; Côte, 2006). Meteorological data from the El Oued station (WMO code: 60559) covering 1989–2019 confirm the absence of a distinct wet season. January is the coldest month, with an average temperature of 12.4 °C, whereas July is the hottest, averaging 37.3 °C. Annual precipitation is low, irregular, and marked by strong interannual variability (Khechekhouche et al., 2020). Winds are frequent and exhibit notable seasonal variability (Voisin, 2004; Nadjah, 1971). During summer, the region is regularly affected by the Sirocco, accompanied by maximum temperatures often exceeding 40.8 °C.

Sampling and vegetation analysis

The floristic inventory of Lake Sif Lemnadi was carried out during the favourable vegetative growth period, in March and April 2019, following several preliminary field surveys. A subjective sampling approach was used to ensure that all plant species occurring at the site were recorded. Vegetation was studied using four rectangular plots measuring 100 m × 25 m (2,500 m² each), positioned at the four cardinal points of the lake (Neffar et al., 2016; Chenchouni, 2017). In each plot, a transect was established from the centre of the water body toward the outer margin in order to cross all vegetation belts associated with different hydrological conditions (Figure 1).

To obtain a detailed characterisation of the dominant halophytic vegetation, a total of 24 quadrats of 4 m² (2 × 2 m) were installed at regular intervals along the transects (6 quadrats per plot). Quadrats were placed so as to represent the main hydrological gradients of the site, including zones corresponding to minimal water level (peripheral dry belt), intermediate/average water level (periodically inundated belt), and maximal water level (proximal humid belt). For each quadrat, this allows the integration of micro-topographic variation into the vegetation analysis.

Within each quadrat, the cover of each species was visually estimated by measuring the area occupied and converting it into a percentage of the total quadrat surface (Van der Maarel, 1979; Neffar et al., 2013; Chenchouni, 2017). Recorded species were identified according to the standard floras of Algeria (Quézel & Santa, 1963; Ozenda, 1983; Halis, 2024), and life forms were classified following Raunkjær's system (Ellenberg & Mueller-Dombois, 1967). This sampling design enabled a consistent assessment of species relative abundance and the floristic composition of the plant communities across the lake's environmental gradients.

Figure 1. Location map of Sif Lemnadi lake (south-east Algeria).

Slika 1. Lokacijski zemljevid jezera Sif Lemnadi (jugovzhodna Alžirija).

Floristic analysis

Species richness (SR), defined as the total number of identified species, was used as the main indicator of plant diversity (Magurran, 2004). The relative abundance (RA) of each family was determined as the proportion of species belonging to that family relative to the total number of recorded species (SR). The frequency of occurrence (Occ) of each species was determined as the ratio between the number of plots where the species was recorded and the total number of plots studied. Species were then classified into four categories (Bigot & Bodot, 1973). To compare floristic composition among plots, Jaccard's similarity index was applied (Magurran, 2004).

This approach allows for the assessment of species diversity, community structure, and the degree of floristic similarity among the different zones of the lake.

Functional characterisation of plants

To better understand the ecological and adaptive strategies of the recorded species, plant functional traits (PFTs) were analysed based on major references (Quézel & Santa, 1962, 1963; Nègre, 1962; Ozenda, 1991) as well as databases such as Tela-Botanica. The approach was based on establishing

two types of biological spectra, expressed as percentages, allowing coherent comparisons between the different phytocological groups and the overall studied flora.

Life forms (Raunkiaer, 1934)

Life forms, defined according to the position of renewal buds and their protection against unfavourable conditions, reflect plant adaptive strategies. Four main categories were considered: i) Chamaephytes: buds located close to the ground, adapted to arid and constrained environments; ii) Hemicryptophytes: buds at ground level, allowing regeneration after climatic stress; iii) Phanerophytes: woody trees and shrubs, characterized by persistent aerial buds; iv) Therophytes: annual plants completing their life cycle within a single favorable season.

Morphological types

Species were also classified according to the persistence of their aerial parts: i) Perennial herbs: surviving for several years through underground organs; ii) Annual plants: completing their cycle in one season and persisting through seeds; iii) Woody plants: trees and shrubs with persistent structures, adapted to long-term survival.

Phytogeographical types

The biogeographical origin of taxa was determined from the main floristic references (Quézel & Santa, 1962, 1963; Ozenda, 1991). Species were assigned to several chorological groups representative of Saharan and Mediterranean flora, such as: i) Saharan endemics; ii) Mediterranean species, iii) Saharo-Arabian species; iv) Cosmopolitan species, etc.

This chorological classification provides insights into the biogeographical processes that shaped the local flora and allows the evaluation of the ecological specificity of the species found in the lake.

Statistical analyses

An agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC) was applied to classify the studied plots according to their floristic composition. Similarity between plots was assessed using Jaccard's index, which accounts for shared species and those specific to each plot.

The resulting similarity matrix was then subjected to AHC using the Unweighted Pair-Group Method with Arithmetic Mean (UPGMA). This method progressively groups the most similar plots to form homogeneous clusters, thereby identifying major trends in floristic structuring.

Results

Floristic composition and structure

The floristic inventory identified 14 vascular plant species, distributed across 14 genera and families (Table 1). The flora of Lake Sif Lemnadi is dominated by *Amaranthaceae* (28.6%), followed by *Poaceae* and *Tamaricaceae* (14.3% each). The other families represented, namely *Cistaceae*, *Apocynaceae*, *Frankeniaceae*, *Plumbaginaceae*, *Juncaceae*, and *Zygophyllaceae*, are each represented by a single species (7.1%).

This distribution highlights the predominance of halophytic families (*Amaranthaceae*, *Tamaricaceae*, *Frankeniaceae*, *Plumbaginaceae*), which are characteristic of saline habitats, while the presence of *Poaceae* reflects a certain degree of ecological heterogeneity. It should be noted that algae were observed in the shallow areas of Lake Sif Lemnadi in low abundance during the study period.

Ecological characteristics of the plant community

Analysis of biological types shows a dominance of chamaephytes (50%), followed by hemicryptophytes (21.4%) and geophytes (14.3%) (Figure 2). The predominance of chamaephytes, whose persistent buds are located close to the ground, reflects the adaptation of species to the arid and saline conditions of the environment. The notable proportion of hemicryptophytes also suggests the presence of species capable of withstanding seasonal drought, while geophytes indicate a survival strategy based on underground storage organs.

Regarding frequency of occurrence, very accidental species and common species predominate, each representing 42.9% of the recorded taxa, while constant species account for only 14.3% (Figure 3). This distribution highlights a relatively heterogeneous and fragmented plant community, where few species are widely distributed, and most have a restricted occurrence.

Morphological and Phytogeographical Spectra

The analysis of morphological types reveals a predominance of herbaceous plants (57.1%), the majority of which are perennial herbs (50%), followed by annual herbs (7.1%). Woody forms account for 42.9% of the recorded flora (Figure 4). This distribution reflects a plant community characterised by the resilience of perennial forms, capable of withstanding arid and saline conditions, and by the significant presence of woody species that stabilise soils and tolerate marked water stress.

From a chorological perspective, the flora of Lake Sif Lemnadi is mainly divided into three major groups (Figure 5). Saharan elements dominate (35.7%), highlighting the ecological imprint of the desert and the adaptation of species to hypersaline and xeric environments. Mediterranean species account for 28.6% of the flora, reflecting the influence of the temperate climate and floristic exchanges between arid and sub-humid zones. Mixed Mediterranean–Saharan taxa represent 14.3%, indicating an ecological transition gradient. It is worth noting that the presence of tropical or tropical–Saharan taxa (14.3%) illustrates the biogeographical diversity of the region and underscores the importance of the lake as a floristic crossroads.

Table 1. Systematic list of plant species recorded around Lake Sif Lemnadi (southeastern Algeria), with their life forms, chorological types, morphological types, frequency, and distribution scale.

Tabela 1. Sistematski seznam rastlinskih vrst, zabeleženih okoli jezera Sif Lemnadi (jugovzhodna Alžirija), z njihovimi življenjskimi oblikami, horološkimi tipi, morfološkimi tipi, pogostostjo in obsegom razširjenosti.

Familles	Scientific Name	Life Form (LF)	Chorological Type (CT)	Morphological Type	Occurrence (%)	scale
Poaceae	<i>Aeluropus littoralis</i> (Gouan) Parl.	Geophyte	Saharan	Perennial herbaceous	30	Common
	<i>Phragmites australis</i> subsp. <i>chrysanthus</i> (Mabille) Soják	Geophyte	Mediterranean	Perennial herbaceous	55	Constent
Amaranthaceae	<i>Cistanche lutea</i> (Desf.) Hoffmanns. & Link	Therophyte	Tropical-Saharan	Annual herbaceous	10	very accidental
	<i>Halochnemum strobilaceum</i> (Pall.) M. Bieb.	Chamaephyte	Saharan	Woody	60	Constent
	<i>Traganum nudatum</i> Delile	Chamaephyte	Saharan	Perennial herbaceous	5	very accidental
	<i>Sarcocornia perennis</i> subsp. <i>alpini</i> (Lag.) Castrov.	Hemicryptophyte	Mediterranean-Saharan	Woody	30	Common
Cistaceae	<i>Helianthemum lippii</i> (L.) Dum.Cours.	Chamaephyte	Mediterranean	Woody	5	very accidental
Apocynaceae	<i>Cynanchum acutum</i> L.	Chamaephyte	Tropical	Perennial herbaceous	5	very accidental
Frankeniaceae	<i>Frankenia pulverulenta</i> subsp. <i>florida</i> (L. Chevall.) Maire	Chamaephyte	Mediterranean	Perennial herbaceous	10	very accidental
Plombaginaceae	<i>Limoniastrum guyonianum</i> Boiss.	Hemicryptophyte	Tropical-Saharan	Woody	20	accidentel
Tamaricaceae	<i>Tamarix gallica</i> L.	Phanerophyte	Mediterranean-Saharan	Woody	45	Common
	<i>Reaumuria vermiculata</i> L.	Chamaephyte	Saharan	Perennial herbaceous	5	very accidental
Juncaceae	<i>Juncus maritimus</i> Lam.	Hemicryptophyte	Mediterranean	Perennial herbaceous	35	Common
Zygophyllaceae	<i>Tetraena alba</i> (L.f.) Beier & Thulin	Chamaephyte	Saharan	Perennial herbaceous	45	Common

Figure 3. Proportion of occurrence frequency categories (C) of vegetation identified in Sif Lemnadi Lake.

Slika 3. Delež kategorij pogostosti pojavljanja (C) vegetacije, identificirane v jezeru Sif Lemnadi.

Figure 4. Proportion of plant morphological types identified in the vegetation of Sif Lemnadi Lake.

Slika 4. Delež morfoloških tipov rastlin, identificiranih v vegetaciji jezera Sif Lemnadi.

Species Occurrence Frequency

The analysis of species occurrence around Lake Sif Lemnadi (Figure 5) reveals a community dominated by very occasional species (42.9%), occurring sporadically and often associated with temporary or marginal microhabitats. Common species account for 35.7% of the flora, reflecting a regular but not permanent establishment across the studied plots. In contrast, occasional species are poorly represented (7.1%), whereas constant species (14.3%) indicate a stable floristic core capable of withstanding strong abiotic constraints, particularly salinity and water fluctuations.

This distribution suggests a generally unstable and heterogeneous vegetation, where few species succeed in establishing themselves durably, while the majority exhibit limited occurrence. Such a configuration is typical of saline and arid environments, where only certain specialised halophytic species form the ecological backbone of the community, while most taxa appear opportunistically or seasonally.

Floristic Diversity and Similarity

Species richness (SR) varies considerably among the studied plots (Table 2). The North plot (N) stands out with the highest floristic richness, with 11 recorded species, followed

by the West plot (W) with nine species and the East plot (E) with seven species. In contrast, the South plot (S) appears to be the least diverse, with only four species.

The analysis of Jaccard similarity indices (CJ) reveals high values between plots N and E (CJ = 0.64), indicating a substantial proportion of shared species. This floristic affinity may result from analogous ecological conditions or environmental gradients that favour the establishment of similar taxa. Intermediate similarities are also observed between N and W (CJ = 0.54) and between W and E (CJ = 0.60), suggesting an ecological continuity among these plots.

By contrast, the S plot shows much lower similarities with the others: S–W (CJ = 0.36) and S–N (CJ = 0.42). These values indicate a relative ecological isolation, probably linked to particular edaphic or hydric conditions that limit the number of shared species.

The overall analysis (Figure 6) thus highlights two contrasting groups:

- N and E form a relatively homogeneous core, characterised by a similar floristic composition and relatively high richness.
- S constitutes a distinct group, marked by reduced and specific flora, reflecting stronger ecological constraints.
- W occupies an intermediate position, showing affinities with N and E but also notable differences with S.

Table 2 reports Jaccard similarity indices (CJ, above diagonal) and the number of shared species (below diagonal). Station codes (N, S, E, W) indicate orientations around the lake, with species richness (SR) shown in the first column.

The hierarchical clustering analysis (HCA) based on these indices highlights the formation of three distinct groups (Figure 6):

1. A first group consisting of the plots located south (S) of the lake, characterised by a restricted and relatively isolated flora.
2. The East plot (E), which stands out as an autonomous group, reflects specific ecological conditions.
3. A third group comprising the North (N) and West (W) plots, reflecting greater floristic homogeneity and marked ecological affinities.

Contribution of dominant halophytes

Overall, vegetation cover at Lake Sif Lemnadi was relatively low, ranging from 11.2% to 24.9% across plots. Species were distributed in parallel bands along the salinity gradient, extending from the centre of the water body toward its margins. This gradient strongly influenced both the distribution and abundance of halophytes, with cover values also varying at the quadrat level.

Dominant species exhibited mean specific cover values between 20% and 30%, with extremes ranging from 4% to 50%. Among them, *Phragmites australis* was the most abundant, with a mean cover of $42.1 \pm 22.8\%$, highlighting its strong competitive ability and high tolerance to saline conditions. It occurred most frequently in plots located near the water body.

Along transects, this species was often interspersed with *Halocnemum strobilaceum* ($17.4 \pm 7.5\%$) and *Tamarix gallica* ($20.1 \pm 7.8\%$), both well represented in peripheral plots. In contrast, *Tetraena alba* appeared as a secondary

component, with a much lower average cover ($3.7 \pm 1.0\%$) (Figure 7).

Discussion

This study provides a detailed quantitative floristic analysis of the permanent saline lake of Sif Lemnadi, located in southern Algeria, a region characterised by extreme desert climatic conditions marked by low rainfall, frequent droughts, and high soil salinity. Worldwide, the number of halophytic species is estimated to range between 2,500 and 3,000, of which about 700 occur in the Mediterranean region (Khan & Dukes, 2001). In the framework of this study, the floristic inventory identified 14 plant species belonging to 9 families. Compared to other wetlands of the High Plateaus and northern Sahara (Chenchouni, 2012; Halis et al., 2012; Neffar et al., 2016; Chenchouni, 2017; Khechekhouche et al., 2020), the floristic richness of Lake Sif Lemnadi can be considered moderate. This level of richness appears to be proportional to the small size of the site and to the severity of its edaphic and climatic conditions.

As observed in other Saharan and steppe ecosystems, most of the species recorded belong to the Amaranthaceae, which are widely represented in saline habitats, and to the Poaceae, which are well adapted to hygrophilous environments. These results confirm that the flora of Lake Sif Lemnadi exhibits a plant assemblage typical of Mediterranean (Öztürk et al., 2011) and North African wetlands (Benabadji et al., 2010; Ghezlaoui et al., 2011; Neffar et al., 2016).

The prevalence of halophilous and thermophilous species in the floristic composition reflects their remarkable ability to adapt to extreme and unstable environments (Neffar et al., 2016). Among them, *Phragmites australis* stands out due to its high cover and ubiquity, confirming its role as an ecosystem engineer capable of altering microhabitat conditions (soil structure, moisture, salinity) and thereby facilitating

Table 2. Proximity matrix applied to floristic similarity among the four sampled plots (by cardinal positions), considered in pairs.

Tabela 2. Matrika bližine, uporabljena za floristično podobnost med štirimi vzorčnimi parcelami (po kardinalnih položajih), obravnavana v parih.

Station	N	W	S	E
N (SR=11)		0,54	0,42	0,64
W (SR=9)	7		0,36	0,60
S (SR=4)	5	4		0,44
E (SR=7)	7	6	4	

Figure 6. Dendrogram of agglomerative hierarchical clustering (AHC) showing species richness (SR) similarity (Jaccard coefficient) among plants recorded at four stations around Lake Sif Lemnadi.

Slika 6. Dendrogram aglomerativnega hierarhičnega združevanja (AHC), ki prikazuje podobnost bogastva vrst (SR) (Jaccardov koeficient) med rastlinami, zabeleženimi na štirih postajah okoli jezera Sif Lemnadi.

Figure 7. Percentage cover of the dominant halophytic species recorded in the vegetation of Lake Sif Lemnadi (southeastern Algeria). Values indicate the relative contribution of each halophyte taxon to the overall community structure.

Slika 7. Odstotek pokritosti prevladujočih halofitnih vrst, zabeleženih v vegetaciji jezera Sif Lemnadi (jugovzhodna Alžirija). Vrednosti kažejo relativni prispevek vsakega halofitnega taksona k celotni strukturi skupnosti.

or limiting the establishment of other taxa. Alongside it, *Halocnemum strobilaceum* and *Tamarix gallica* play a key role in stabilising saline soils, while *Tetraena alba* appears as a secondary taxon, indicative of drier and more peripheral conditions. The spatial structuring of vegetation into parallel bands observed along the salinity gradient reflects a phenomenon of ecological segregation commonly found in North African chotts and sebkhas. This pattern supports the observations of Le Houérou (1992) and Neffar et al. (2018) regarding the strong influence of salinity and seasonal drought on the distribution of halophytic communities.

The site also hosts perennial species adapted to harsh climatic conditions (Khechekhouche et al., 2020). The vegetation is mainly composed of perennial herbaceous plants (50%) and shrubs (42.9%). These taxa exhibit adaptations not only to the high soil salinity but also to the long periods of summer heat. Most of them possess xero-halophytic traits that enable them to withstand such environmental constraints (Tug et al., 2012).

The spectrum of life forms is dominated by chamaephytes (50%), reflecting the typical influence of the Mediterranean semi-arid bioclimate (Medjahdi et al., 2009; Salama et al., 2014). These chamaephytes, entirely halophytic, are distinguished by their high tolerance to drought and salinity, unlike phanerophytes (Ellenberg & Mueller-Dombois, 1967; Ghezlaoui et al., 2011). Their widespread distribution around the lake is probably favoured by the absence of grazing, since livestock generally avoids saline plants (Neffar et al., 2016). Hemicryptophytes rank second, which may be related to the high organic matter content of soils (Bardgett et al., 2005).

The floristic distribution around the lake results from a complex interaction of several environmental factors, whether abiotic, biotic, or anthropogenic (Rozema et al., 1985; Alvarez-Rogel et al., 2007; Minggagud & Yang, 2013). According to Brown (2006), the mosaic structure of plant communities reflects the heterogeneity of environmental conditions, particularly soil moisture and salinity. Floristic diversity is also influenced by landscape organisation, land abandonment practices, and grazing regimes (Muñoz & Alcántara, 2013; Lomba et al., 2013).

Plots located to the north and west of Lake Sif Lemnadi exhibit relatively high floristic richness and homogeneity, whereas the southern plot remains the least diverse. This difference appears to be linked to the excess water from irrigation of the palm grove situated to the north, which carries residues of agricultural fertilisers. This additional water

input modifies the chemical and nutrient conditions of the habitat, thereby promoting the growth of certain species. However, the high soil salinity in the southern part limits vegetation development and reduces biodiversity (Bijos et al., 2023). In general, the vegetation of desert wetlands follows a concentric arrangement determined by a gradient of salinity and moisture (Koull, 2023).

Salinity is recognised as the main factor controlling the development, zonation, and density of vegetation in saline wetlands (Rozema et al., 1985; Alvarez-Rogel et al., 2007; Halis et al., 2012; Neffar et al., 2016; Chenchouni, 2017). The accumulation of salts in the soil reduces the water potential and limits water availability for plants, rendering the habitat physiologically dry (Djebaili, 1978). Variation in total vegetation cover also appears to depend on the distance and orientation of plots in relation to the water body, with halophytes colonising the saline margins (Aboura et al., 2006).

In these habitats, edaphic factors play a major role in the survival and distribution of species (Chenchouni, 2017). Salinity, moisture, and waterlogging strongly condition the floristic composition (Ji et al., 2009; Cott et al., 2013; González-Alcaraz et al., 2014). Several studies have shown that halophytic communities, whether coastal or inland, are closely dependent on such edaphic gradients. However, little research has focused on inland saline habitats in North Africa, particularly in arid and semi-arid wetlands (Chenchouni, 2012; El Ghani et al., 2014; Koull & Chehma, 2015; Neffar et al., 2016).

The results obtained at Sif Lemnadi confirm the observations made in other saline wetlands of the country. At Sabkha Djendli, vegetation follows a decreasing salinity gradient from the interior outward (Chenchouni, 2017). A similar pattern is observed in Chott El Gharbi, in western Algeria (Benabadji et al., 2010). Likewise, Khaznadar et al. (2009) and Bezzalla et al. (2019) showed that the distribution of halophytes depends on salinity, moisture, soil texture, temperature, water depth, and flooding duration. Finally, Gomaa (2012) highlighted that although electrical conductivity (EC) and specific resistance (SR) are correlated with vegetation cover, other factors may also influence community organisation.

Conclusion

This study highlights the ecological importance of Lake Sif Lemnadi as a refuge for specialised halophytic flora adapted to the extreme salinity and aridity of the northern Sahara.

This study highlights the ecological importance of Lake Sif Lemnadi as a refuge for specialised halophytic flora adapted to the extreme salinity and aridity of the northern Sahara. Overall, our findings met the objectives defined in this study by providing a comprehensive description of the floristic diversity and ecological strategies of species inhabiting Lake Sif Lemnadi. The analysis of life-form spectra and halophytic adaptations confirmed the predominance of xero-halophytic traits that structure plant communities under strong edaphic constraints. Similarly, the clear spatial zonation observed along the moisture and salinity gradients reflects a robust ecological pattern widely reported in Mediterranean and North African saline wetlands. Beyond their descriptive value, these results provide an essential baseline for the future monitoring of Saharan wetland vegetation. Given the sensitivity of these habitats to hydrological fluctuations, land use changes, and increasing salinisation, the floristic and ecological data provided here can support conservation planning and the development of sustainable management strategies aimed at preserving the unique biodiversity of desert wetlands.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, B.B. and E.A.K.; methodology, B.B. and E.A.K.; investigation, B.B., E.A.K., Z.A., L.A., M.N., B.K., and

G.A.D.; formal analysis, B.B., Z.A. and E.A.K.; data curation, B.B. and E.A.K.; writing-original draft preparation, B.B. and E.A.K.; writing-review and editing, all authors; supervision, B.K. and G.A.D. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

The datasets generated and analysed during the current study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18173229>

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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